

MACSI FLIGHT SUMMARY

for

U.K. MRF Hercules

29 March 1995 to 10 April 1995

RSI Aircraft Scientists

R.W. Saunders, S.J. English, D.C. Jones

Report Prepared

by

Steve English

MetO(RSI)

Contents

1 Introduction.	3
2 Instrumentation	3
2.1 Aircraft	3
2.1.1 UK C-130	3
2.1.2 Skyvan	4
2.1.3 Do-228	5
2.1.4 Gulfstream	5
2.2 C-130 Instrument Performance Summary.	6
3 MACSI 30th March 1995	7
4 MACSI 31th March 1995	9
5 MACSI 2nd April 1995	11
6 MACSI 4th April 1995	12
7 MACSI 5th April 1995	14
8 MACSI 6th April 1995	16
9 MACSI 7th April 1995	17
10 Flight summaries.	20
11 Satellite overpass times	20
12 Flight track plots.	20
13 Weather summaries and synoptic charts.	20
14 Sea ice charts	20
15 Other Information Available	22
16 Appendix A	23
17 Appendix B	24
18 Appendix C	31

1 Introduction.

Successful use of microwave radiometer data in numerical weather prediction requires that emission and scattering by the surface is parameterised in a realistic way in the radiative transfer model. The ESA recognised the need for more measurements by airborne radiometers and synthetic aperture radar (SAR) and provided financial backing for an international experiment (MACSI) in Finland Mar–Jun 1995. The C-130 with two airborne microwave radiometers (MARSS and Deimos) participated during the spring melt part of MACSI (Mar 29–Apr 9). The sea ice in the Gulf of Bothnia represented a microcosm of new and young ice types. Dark and light nilas, pancake and grease ice were all observed as well as rafting, including finger rafting. Often the ice was heavily ridged but equally there were areas of flat ice. The snow cover was variable, changing frequently during the experiment. Overall the ice extent was significantly less than that expected from climatology as a result of very warm weather from late January to early March. Precipitation had, however, been above normal and the snow cover inland was thick and usually composed of three distinct layers. During the measurement campaign the weather was rather cold with periods of mostly light snow.

2 Instrumentation

2.1 Aircraft

The participating aircraft were the UK Meteorological Research Flight (MRF) C-130, the HUT Skyvan (radiometers at 6.8 [V & H], 10.7 [V & H], 18.7 [V & H], 24, 34, 94 [V & H] and a SAR) and a Do228 from Deutsche Forschungsanstalt für Luft und Raumfahrt (DLR) (C, L and P band SAR “ESAR”). Shortly before and after the experiment a Gulfstream jet equipped with a Danish SAR “EMISAR” also overflew the test sites (C and L band).

2.1.1 UK C-130

Aircraft performance details

- Normal flying altitude - 150m to 1500m (maximum 9km).
- cruising speed - 75 ms^{-1} when overflying test sites.
- Endurance - Upto 11 hours though the longest flight on MACSI was just over 8 hours.

Basic meteorological parameters

1. Temperature.

- Rosemount de-iced and non-deiced sensors.

2. Wind.

- Pitot-static sensor and wind vanes measure flow relative to the aircraft. Aircraft velocity components relative to the ground measured by Inertial Navigation System (INS). INS Schuler and drift errors corrected by reference to Global Positioning System (GPS) navigation data.

3. Humidity.

- General-Eastern 1011B dew/frost point hygrometer.

Cloud microphysical parameters

1. Particle size spectra.

- **Forward Scattering Spectrometer Probe (FSSP)** measuring water droplets in the size range 0.5 to 47 μm diameter with some capacity for the detection of small ice crystals (although this is currently only qualitative).
- **2D Optical Array Probes (OAP)** measuring in the size ranges 25 – 800 μm (2D-C) and 200 – 6400 μm (2D-P).
- **Passive Cavity Aerosol Spectrometer Probe (PCASP)** measuring aerosol particles in the size range 0.1 to 3 μm diameter.

Three mounting points are available for these probes, and it is normal to carry the FSSP, 2D-C, and either the PCASP or 2D-P.

2. Bulk water measurements.

- **Johnson-Williams liquid water content (LWC) hot-wire probe.**
- **Evaporative Total Water Content (TWC) probe:** a Lyman- α hygrometer referenced to the General Eastern instrument.

Radiation measurements

1. Microwave measurements. MARSS (Microwave Airborne Radiometer Scanning System).

- Two channels at 89 and 157 GHz.
- Scans along the aircraft track from zenith to nadir in 10° steps to 40° (assuming no aircraft pitch).

2. Microwave measurements. Deimos (Named after the first moon of Mars).

- Two channels at 23.8 and 50.3 GHz.
- Scans along the aircraft track from nadir in 10° steps to 40° (assuming aircraft pitch of 5°).

3. Broad-band measurements. Both upward- and downward-looking sets of clear-dome pyranometers (0.3 to 3.0 μm), red-dome pyranometers (0.7 to 3.0 μm), and Foot-type pyrgeometers (4 to 50 μm).

Other measurements

1. **Air samples were collected and stored in order to measure methane concentrations as a contribution to the TIGER project. Unexpected variations in methane concentration were found. Samples were collected during flights A376 and A379 over the Finnish test sites and flight A382 over the Barents sea.**

2.1.2 Skyvan

Aircraft performance details

- **Flying altitude** - 300m during scientific flying.
- **cruising speed** - 55 ms^{-1} during scientific flying.
- **Endurance** - 2 hours, typical.

Radiation measurements

- Radiometer at 24, 34 and 94 GHz. This, the older of two radiometers worked well during the experiment. The 94 GHz channel supplied dual polarized data. The 94 GHz channel detected the Oulu ATC radar, giving small spikes in the data at 14-15s intervals when near Oulu. This was operated over snow sites 4/4/95 and sea ice and snow sites 5/4/95.
- Radiometer at 6.8, 10.7 and 18.7 GHz. The 6.8 GHz channel was contaminated by occasional interference from mobile phone transmitters at 900MHz. Otherwise this new radiometer worked well. Only one of the 6.8 and 10.7 GHz could be used at any one time. This was operated over snow sites 4/4/95 and sea ice and snow sites 5/4/95.
- SAR. As an alternative to the radiometers a SAR could be fitted. This was operated on 6/4/95.

2.1.3 Do-228

Aircraft performance details

- Normal flying altitude 3.3km (FL110).
- cruising speed - 85 ms^{-1}
- endurance - 4 to 5 hours

Radiation measurements

- L, C, P band SAR (ESAR). The SAR was operated successfully and first look measurements are available by exabyte. It is likely not all the channels will be available due to a partial failure on the first flight.

2.1.4 Gulfstream

Aircraft performance details

- Normal flying altitude 5.4km (FL180).

Radiation measurements

- L, C band SAR. The SAR was operated successfully on 22/3/95 though the status of later flights is not known at time of writing. This SAR (EMISAR) was not used during the C-130 involvement.

MRF Flight No.	A	A	A	A	A	A	A
	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
	7	7	7	7	8	8	8
	6	7	8	9	0	1	2
Static Pressure	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Pitot Pressure	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Gust Vanes	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N
De-iced Temp	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Non De-iced Temp	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
ICTP	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
GE Hygrometer	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Total Water	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y ⁵
Johnson Williams	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
FSSP	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
2D Cloud	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
2D Precip	Y ¹						
Upper BBRs	Y ²						
Lower BBRs	Y ²						
Heiman	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
MARSS	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Deimos	Y ³	Y ³	Y ⁴				
INS	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
OMEGA	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
GPS	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y

Table 1: Instrument status

Y Instrument was operated.

N Instrument was not operated or failed to operate.

Note 1 The 2DP gave unreliable results.

Note 2 The BBRs took upto one hour to operate normally after take off

Note 3 Deimos data not recorded. NB manual recording by Deimos operator available

Note 4 Deimos data recorded but polarizer not working.

Note 5 Total water unreliable at times.

2.2 C-130 Instrument Performance Summary.

Table 1 summarizes the instruments used on each C-130 flight and gives an indication of how they performed during the flight.

3 MACSI 30th March 1995

C-130 Flight: A376
Take Off: 08:50 UTC
Land: 14:55 UTC

3.1 An assessment of the flight.

A successful flight over the Gulf of Bothnia and Northern Finland. Weather was ideal with clear skies all day. The ice was confined to the north of the Gulf of Bothnia but did cover the three most northerly ice sites. The southernmost site was in an active danger area and consequently could not be reached. The ice varied from fast ice in the north to ridged, snow covered ice and light nilas further south. There were a number of leads, some of which were quite wide, but there were no extensive areas of open water. After flying the ice sites we flew around the danger area to reach open water to the south both to check the Deimos polarization and to obtain data over a cold and very calm sea area.

After a return leg over the ice sites we transited to the snow sites. Near Oulu the snow cover was not complete in agricultural areas, although generally it was about 20cm deep. As we flew inland the ground elevation rose slowly and the snow cover increased. Also the forest cover increased at first before reaching a mix of dense forest, young forest (with wide gaps) and a few open spaces. At first wider rivers were free of ice but further inland most rivers were frozen and snow covered. We overflew a few small lakes which were always frozen and snow covered. Visibility remained excellent throughout. We flew at 1000' and 4000' over both ice sites and snow sites and FL250 back over ice sites. MARSS worked OK throughout. Deimos data for 23.8 GHz was obtained but only by written log (no data was recorded) and no data from the 50.3 GHz channel was obtained. No LN2 calibrations were possible. 60 bags were filled for methane sampling.

3.2 Summary of the weather conditions.

A slack south westerly airstream over the area with a warm front well to the west which gave very thin and broken cirrus later in the flight. Surface air temperatures were -5 to -2 °C over the ice sites. Clear skies persisted throughout

Run	Start	End	Height	Hdg	Comments
P1	090413	091820	FL100 to 50'	200	Clear air over bkn ice.
Transit to sea ice test sites point A					
O1	092246	092347	1000'	090 ¹	Stbd 45° over A'
O2	092347	092447	1000'	090 ¹	Stbd 45° over A'
R1.1	092540	092834	1000'	355	A' to B
O3	092834	092932	1000'	090 ¹	Stbd 45° over B
O4	092932	093032	1000'	090 ¹	Stbd 45° over B
R1.2	093102	094140	1000'	010	B to C
O5	094140	094239	1000'	040 ¹	Stbd 45° over C
O6	094239	094336	1000'	040 ¹	Stbd 45° over C
R1.3	094455	095347	1000'	010	C to D
O7	100045	100148	1000'	160 ¹	Stbd 45° over D
O8	100148	100810	1000'	160 ¹	Stbd 45° over D
O9	100810	100908	1000'	060 ¹	Stbd 45° over D
O10	100908	101010	1000'	060 ¹	Stbd 45° over D
R2.1	101312	102617	1000'	210	D to C
R2.2	102617	103536	1000'	210	C to B
R2.3	103536	104536	1000'	210	B to A'
P2	104734	105511	500' to 4000'	015/205	Clear air over bkn ice
R3.1	105700	110311	4000'	020	A' to B
R3.2	110311	111331	4000'	020	B to C
R3.3	111331	112443	4000'	020	C to D
Transit to snow test sites point E					
R4.1	113946	114143	1000'	035	E to F
R4.2	114143	115504	1000'	045	F to G
R4.3	115504	120437	1000'	040	G to H
R4.4	120437	120630	1000'	040	Over H
P3	121115	121501	500' to 4000'	240	Clear air over H
R5.1	121501	122522	4000'	230	H to G
R5.2	122522	123631	4000'	230	G to F
R5.3	123631	123856	4000'	230	F to E
R5.4	123856	124054	4000'	230	Over E
Transit to sea ice test sites point D					
R6.1	125729	130949	1000'	210	D to C
R6.2	130949	132036	1000'	210	C to B
R6.3	132036	134421	1000'	205	B to A
Transit to open water avoiding danger area					
O11	134321	134421	1000'	270 ¹	Stbd 45° over A
O12	134421	134520	1000'	270 ¹	Stbd 45° over A
R7	135310	135044	1000'	230	Over open water
P4	135310	141923	50' to FL250	070/010	Clear air, open water
R8	141923	143923	FL250	010/030	Calibration run

Table 2: A376 30th March 1995

Note 1 Point A' used instead of point A when danger area active.

Note 2 ¹ Starting heading during orbit runs.

4 MACSI 31th March 1995

C-130 Flight: A377
Take Off: 09:50 UTC
Land: 13:35 UTC

3.1 An assessment of the flight.

A successful flight over the sea ice sites only. The ice had moved about 1 mile southwards and new ice had formed on the southern edge. Site Alpha (I1) was reached as the danger area was inactive in the morning and was in ice. Further north large leads had appeared. The level ice in the north was thickly snow covered. The ridged ice and new ice further south were mostly snow free, though snow often covered the ridges. MARSS worked well and both LN2 and high level calibration data was obtained. Deimos 23.8 GHz was logged by hand but still did not record on the aircraft data recording system. The 50 GHz channel was u/s until shortly before the end of the flight.

An initial run southwards at 4000' to obtain lower resolution radiometer data was followed by orbits and a short run over open water for Deimos, at 500' to minimise the atmospheric attenuation between aircraft and surface. The return A to D was at the standard flight altitude of 1000ft followed by additional orbits over site D. Then we flew south again at 500' to obtain a detailed record of the ice type and surface condition. Finally we profiled through cloud to FL250 to obtain very low resolution data over the ice sites and also as a calibration run for the MARSS. Deimos had problems at very cold temperatures at high altitude. No runs were carried out over the snow sites as it was felt conditions would not have changed significantly from the previous flight.

3.2 Summary of the weather conditions.

Weather conditions were again ideal with clear skies most of the day and excellent visibility. Later in the flight a sheet of sc came in from the west and obscured the view of the surface for the high level runs. There was also some thin ci present.

Run	Start	End	Height	Hdg	Comments
Transit to site D					
R1.1	100729	100841	4000'	205	Over site D
R1.2	100841	102151	4000'	205	D to C
R1.3	102151	103515	4000'	205	C to B
R1.4	103515	104659	4000'	205	B to A
P1	104750	105441	4000' to 50'	220	Clear air, over A
O1	105537	105638	500'	280 ¹	Stbd 45° open water
O2	105638	105735	500'	280 ¹	Stbd 45° open water
R2.1	110003	110505	500'	200	Over open water
R2.2	110703	111204	500'	030	Over open water
R3.1	111621	112515	1000'	080	A to B
R3.2	112515	113420	1000'	025	B to C
R3.3	113420	114319	1000'	030	C to D
R3.4	114319	114529	1000'	270	Over site D
O3	114529	114630	1000'	270 ¹	Over site D
O4	114630	114730	1000'	270 ¹	Over site D
R4.1	115000	115057	500'	200	Over site D
R4.2	115057	120113	500'	200	D to C, over R/V Aranda
R4.3	120113	121129	500'	200	C to B, sc above
R4.4	121129	122259	500'	200	B to A, sc above
P2	122705	125522	50' to FL250	200	Through sc, over A
R5	125558	131059	FL250	205	Calibration run
R6	131242	132243	FL250	200/020	Calibration run

Table 3: A377 31th March 1995

Run	Start	End	Height	Hdg	Comments
P1	110521	112332	FL170 - 500'	330	Over site D
Transit to snow test sites point E					
R1.1	114237	115813	500'	045	E to G
R1.2	115813	120305	500'	045	G to lake ice
R1.3	120414	120708	500'	145	Over lake ice
R2.1	120844	121131	500'	350	Over lake ice
R2.2	121620	121829	500'	145	lake ice to H
R3.1	122133	122329	500'	220	H to G
R3.2	122329	123334	500'	215	G to F
R3.3	123334	125045	500'	210	F to E
Transit to sea ice test sites point D					
R4.1	130759	130845	500'	205	Over D
R4.2	130845	131817	500'	200	D to C
R4.3	131817	132705	500'	200	C to B
R4.4	132705	133113	500'	220	B to A
P2	133258	135341	500' to FL250	020	Over A
R5.1	135358	140858	FL250	190	Calibration run
R5.2	141058	142059	FL250	025	Calibration run

Table 4: A378 2nd April 1995

5 MACSI 2nd April 1995

C-130 Flight: A378
 Take Off: 10:55 UTC
 Land: 14:30 UTC

3.1 An assessment of the flight.

A partially successful runs over all the MACSI test sites. We initially flew to the ice test sites but this was abandoned due to adverse weather and we transited to snow site E. In order to get below cloud the run over the snow sites was at 500'. Between sites H and G we overflow an adjacent lake. The return leg was also at 500'. On reaching site E it was decided to see if the weather conditions over the ice sites had improved sufficiently for a run to be possible. We were fortunate to be able to complete a run at 500' though the visibility of the surface was at times very poor. The final run was aborted early as we were not able to determine any surface features. We then profiled to FL250 to complete a calibration run for the MARSS. Again MARSS worked very well and Deimos data recorded on the DRS for the first time and both Deimos channels worked. However the dual polarization did not work and the Deimos computer crashed on three occasions. Also Deimos stops working when very cold at high altitude.

3.2 Summary of the weather conditions.

We were in a gentle but very unstable north-westerly with a low pressure centre just to the north (over Kemi). Frequent heavy snow showers reduced visibility on a number of occasions though the evidence from both the PMS data and the MARSS zenith views when flying below cloud was that the LWP through the clouds was very small — they were almost completely in the ice phase.

6 MACSI 4th April 1995

C-130 Flight: A379
Take Off: 08:29 UTC
Land: 13:51 UTC

3.1 An assessment of the flight.

The intercomparison flight over the snow sites was successfully carried out with the Skyvan following the C-130 about 15 mins later. Three of the snow sites were visually identified. The radiometers on both aircraft were working OK but we had to deviate from the track at one point to avoid cloud. The lake site was again flown over. A time check between the Skyvan and the C-130 indicated the Skyvan was 12secs ahead of the C-130 time. Owing to adverse weather conditions the Skyvan only flew the snow sites.

The remainder of the C-130 flight was over ice sites A to D. There was low cloud over part of the track around site C which only allowed runs at 1000' and 4000'. The DLR DO-228 was at FL110 with a SAR looking down at the ice sites. Three of the 4 ice sites were visually located with flags or the ship.

About 65 bags were filled over the snow and ice sites during the flight for measuring methane concentrations.

There were problems with the SATCOM via Goonhilly but messages were received via Singapore. The 2D-P probe did not perform well after the high level runs. The lower BBRs did not come until an hour into flight.

3.2 Summary of the weather conditions.

A slack cyclonic region with convective clouds giving snow showers over the land. The wind from the surface to FL200 was less than 20 knots. St clouds were over parts of the sea ice with base below 500'.

Table 5: A379 4th April 1995

Run	Start	End	Height	Hdg	Comments
R1.1	084030	084239	1000'	045	Over site E
R1.2	084239	084425	1000'	045	E to F
R1.3	084425	085910	1000'	045	F to just short of G
R1.4	085910	090012	500'	050	Over G
R1.5	090151	090907	1000'	050	G to H
R2.1	091248	091836	500'	220	H to lake ice
R2.2	091918	092201	500'	150	Over lake ice
R2.3	092411	092638	500'	340	Over lake ice
R2.4	092638	093044	500'	230	Lake ice to G
R2.5	093044	094427	500'	230	G to F
R2.6	094427	094626	500'	220	F to E
R2.7	094626	094830	500'	220	Over E
Transit to snow sites point E.					
O1	101944	102043	1000'	230'	Sbdl 45° over A
O2	102043	102142	1000'	230'	Sbdl 45° over A
R3.1	102236	103510	1000'	015	A to B
O3	103522	103622	1000'	060'	Sbdl 45° over B
O4	103622	103718	1000'	060'	Sbdl 45° over B
R3.2	103934	104816	1000'	015	B to C
O5	104826	104922	1000'	060'	Sbdl 45° over C
O6	104922	105020	1000'	060'	Sbdl 45° over C
R3.3	105106	105827	1000'	015	C to D
R3.4	105827	105930	1000'	030	Over D
O7	105938	110033	1000'	060'	Sbdl 45° over D
O8	110033	110129	1000'	060'	Sbdl 45° over D
R4.1	110433	110601	4000'	190	Over D
R4.2	111218	113030	4000'	200	D to C
R4.3	113030	114309	4000'	220	C to B
P1	114631	120906	50' to FL200	025	Over B
R5.1	120906	121907	FL200	020	Calibration run
R5.2	122047	123546	FL200	205	Calibration run
O9	124856	124954	1000'	270'	Sbdl 45° over A
O10	124954	125051	1000'	270'	Sbdl 45° over A
O9	125118	125212	1000'	210'	Port 45° over A
O10	125212	125309	1000'	210'	Port 45° over A
R6.1	125506	130739	1000'	030	A to B
R6.2	130739	131848	1000'	025	B to C
R6.3	131848	132714	1000'	020	C to D
R6.4	132714	132819	1000'	020	Over D

7 MACSI 5th April 1995

C-130 Flight: A380
Take Off: 07:57 UTC
Land: 13:10 UTC

1. An assessment of the flight

A highly successful flight over both the ice and snow sites. An intercomparison run with the HUT Skyvan radiometers was also performed.

After take off, a transit to A followed by $2 \times 45^\circ$ starboard and $2 \times 45^\circ$ port orbits were performed. Following 10 mins behind the Skyvan, an intercomparison run at 1000 ft from A to D was carried out with varying amounts of cirrus present above the aircraft. It is not expected that this will have a significant effect on the radiometer measurements. A reciprocal run using updated GPS positions followed this. During the runs a suitable area for performing a clover leaf pattern over heavily ridge ice was identified. It was observed that most of the leads that had developed between the floes of old ice had refrozen. Point A, the most southerly site was in a region of nilas with some grease ice.

A profile at 1000 ft/min from A along the test line permitted PMS measurements through the cirrus which was less than 1000 ft thick with a maximum 2DC count of about 500/l. A run at FL200 with clear skies above provided excellent calibration data for the MARSS. Following a quick descent down to A, a run at 2000ft QNH to C in formation with the Skyvan was executed for aerial photography and filming. A clover leaf pattern over a heavily ridged area of older partially snow-covered ice was then flown to allow any azimuthal dependence of ice emissivity to be determined. Careful study of the video and stills taken during all the passes over this area will be needed to determine the degree to which the ridging displayed a preferred direction.

Runs over the snow and lake sites (E to H) at 1000ft were carried out followed by a return run at 4000 ft over the snow sites only. Thin liquid water cloud at just below 4000 ft did not affect the radiometer channels significantly.

On our return to Oulu, 50 ft runs over both runways were performed (one dry and the other snow covered) for comparison with the HUT Skyvan measurements which use this as a validation of their radiometer calibrations. Passes at 500 ft and 1000 ft over the apron to verify the downward-facing video FOV were executed before landing.

In summary, all the scientific objectives of this flight were achieved with many visual fixes of the site markers confirming accurate navigation. Both MARSS and Deimos functioned well throughout.

2. Summary of the weather conditions.

A relatively slack cyclonic region to the SE of a low pressure system with an associated weak trough passing through the area. Although some Ci and Sc were present during the experiment, the cloud was never extensive or thick enough to seriously affect the radiometer channels.

Table 6: A380 5th April 1995

Run	Start	End	Height	Hdg	Comments
R1	081650	081751	1000'		Sb'd 45° over A
O2	081748	081848	1000'		Sb'd 45° over A
O3	081907	082003	1000'		Port 45° over A
O4	082003	082055	1000'		Port 45° over A
R1.1	082825	084102	1000'		A to B. Skyvan at B
R1.2	084102	085127	1000'		B to C
R1.3	085127	085934	1000'		C to D
R1.3	085934	090030	1000'		Over D
R2.1	090438	090540	1000'		Over D
R2.2	090540	091443	1000'		D to C
R2.3	091443	092620	1000'		C to B
R2.4	092620	093939	1000'		B to A
P2	094622	100507	50' to FL200		In clear air over A
R3	100709	102505	FL200		Calibration run over A to D)
Descend to 1000' for clover leaf pattern over ridged area					
R4.1	110624	110726	1000'		Start of clover leaf
R4.2	110838	110934	1000'		050
R4.3	111127	111236	1000'		270
R4.4	111423	111518	1000'		145
R4.5	111657	111803	1000'		350
R4.6	111940	112111	1000'		230
R4.7	112252	112353	1000'		090
R4.8	112540	112650	1000'		305
Transit to snow site point E					
R5.1	114248	114433	1000'		050
R5.2	114433	114622	1000'		Over E
R5.3	114622	115732	1000'		E to F
R5.4	115732	115941	1000'		F to G
R5.5	115941	120318	1000'		Over G
R5.6	120318	120609	1000'		G to Lake ice
R5.7	120808	121044	1000'		Over lake ice
R5.8	121510	121707	1000'		Over lake ice
R6.1	122000	122218	1000'		Lake ice to H
R6.2	122218	123040	4000'		Over H
R6.3	123040	123258	4000'		H to G
R6.4	123258	124731	4000'		G to F
R6.5	124731	124943	4000'		F to E
R7	125830	125857	50'		Over E
Runway calibration run					

8 MACSI 6th April 1995

C-130 Flight: A381
Take Off: 09:50 UTC
Land: 13:35 UTC

1. An assessment of the flight

A successful flight in clear air over open water to the south of the sea ice test sites was completed to measure microwave radiative transfer in a very dry atmosphere. A long calibration run was completed at FL200 also overflying the ice sites.

After transit to the operating area a profile from 50ft to 2000ft was completed. Runs along a heading of about 236° were flown at a number of heights (2000ft, 5000ft, FL100, FL140, FL200) with profile climb between levels. The water vapour burden was measured at only 5 to 6mm, a fact confirmed by the MARSS 89 and 157 GHz brightness temperatures. MARSS worked very well but the Deimos software occasionally needed re-booting. The Deimos dump on HORACE did not give meaningful numbers so the Deimos data could not be interpreted on flight. At each level a southwestward leg and reciprocal leg were flown. The 2DP did not work properly. All other instruments worked well.

The final reciprocal leg was extended northwards over the sea ice test sites. The sea ice had retreated northwards and was much more compact. Almost all the ice was light nilas or snow covered nilas but there was extensive grease ice near the ice edge.

2. Summary of the weather conditions.

A vigorous low was tracking to the south of the operating area and a bank of cirrus cloud was present to the south. A thin sheet of cirrus associated with this extended over the southern half of the runs, with 1/8 As and 1/8 St but the northern half was clear. All the cloud was much too thin to have any affect on the radiometer channels.

Run	Start	End	Height	Hdg	Comments
Transit to open water to southwest of site A					
P1	081632	082007	50' to 2000'	230	Over open water
R1.1	082454	083555	2000'	215	Ci to south
R1.2	083922	084824	2000'	030	
P2	084824	085256	2000' to 5000'	Spiral	
R2.1	085427	090528	5000'	220	
R2.2	090852	091753	5000'	030	
P3	091812	092228	5000' to FL100	025	Ci to south thicker
R3.1	092358	093359	FL100	210	
R3.2	093731	094733	FL100	035	
P4	094838	095223	FL100 to FL140	030	
R4.1	095444	100445	FL140	220	
R4.2	100833	101947	FL140	030	
P5	102008	102518	FL140 to FL200	030	
R5.1	102541	103542	FL200	225	Calibration runs
R5.2	103921	110051	FL200	030	Extended over A to D
Transit to Lulea for LOX then transit to Oulu and lan—					

Table 7: A381 6th April 1995

9 MACSI 7th April 1995

C-130 Flight: A382
 Take Off: 07:52 UTC
 Land: 16:06 UTC

1. An assessment of the flight

A successful flight over the Barents sea between 75N and 78.5N and 25E and 28E to measure the microwave properties of sea ice in the open ocean to compare with the lower salinity ice in the Gulf of Bothnia.

A profile was carried out down into the area which showed a dry air mass above the area. Two orbits were obtained over open water. A run northwards along 28E was then commenced starting over open water at 1000'. Ice blink was observed on the horizon at 100051 at 74.2N 28.4E and the ice edge, which was very well defined and consisted of pancake ice, was reached at 104832 at 76.6N 28E. Shortly after reaching the ice edge a sheet of low stratus was encountered which initially we climbed to 1500' to avoid but subsequently dropped to 500' as we could not see the surface. The ice soon changed to ridged and snow covered first year ice. North of 77N the cloud disappeared though it remained misty at times and we returned to 1000'. There was evidence of small amounts of liquid water in the cloud from both the PMS and MARSS instruments. There were occasional leads but the ice was more compact than the Finnish ice. On reaching 78.5N 28E we flew an orbit over compact and heavily ridged ice. As visibility was falling we descended to 500' to retain good visual of the ice surface. After briefly flying along the 78.5N parallel we turned to fly south along 27E to 77.5N. In this region some multi-year ice was observed. It was very thick, with sastrugi, and quite different to the young ice found in the Gulf of Bothnia. Following this we flew west to 26E and then north again to 78.5N over similar ice types, though areas of brash ice were observed. These runs were all at 1000'. Another orbit

run was flown at 78.5N 25E. The final leg, flying south along 25E, started at 1000' but later was forced down to 500' as we again encountered stratus near the ice edge. As we approached Svalbard a number of tabular icebergs were observed a few of which were overflown. Also the ice type changed to dark nilas with a high concentration of ice cakes in the nilas. At the nilas edge an extensive area of grease ice was observed, with a low concentration of ice cakes, before open water was reached again at around 76N 25E.

Another orbit run over open water was flown before profiling over open water to FL250 for a calibration run for MARSS. This run was extended over the north of Norway for a long cross section of snow covered semi-mountainous land. Good calibration data was recorded.

The radiometers worked well throughout and most of the runs were clear of cloud. Hand-held video, 35mm slides and voice descriptions of the ice state were recorded throughout the low level runs in addition to the normal downward video.

Seventy bags were filled during the flight for the methane study.

There were no significant instrument problems although the General Eastern was having difficulty at low levels when we started the profile back up.

2. Summary of the weather conditions.

The whole operating area was in a slack north easterly airstream with mainly clear skies over the ice. There was low stratus over the ice edge which rapidly became convective cloud over the open sea. Visibility was highly variable but generally good enough for the ice observations.

Run	Start	End	Height	Hdg	Comments
Transit to north to start calibration run over snow covered land					
R1	083930	085936	FL230	355	Over snow covered land
P1	093824	100325	FL230 to 50'	350	Through cu layer
O1	101552	101747	1000'	360 ¹	Over open water
Transit north over open water to ice edge					
R2	104832	105516	1000'	355	Over pancake ice
R3	105557	105959	1500'	355	Above cloud
R4	110050	113800	1000'	360	Over ridged ice
O2	113808	113913	1000'	050 ¹	Stbd 45°
R5	114108	114422	500'	265	Misty
R6	114454	120721	500'	170	Some multiyear ice
R7	120757	121157	500'	265	Misty
R8	121238	123901	500'	360	Misty
R9	123939	124353	1000'	270	
O3	124412	124508	1000'	290	
R10	124631	132718	1000'	165	Icebergs. Some open water
R11	132801	134742	500'	165	Dark nilas
O4	134754	134852	500'	200	Stbd 45°
P2	135003	141628	50' to FL250	165	Through cloud layer
R12	142925	144928	FL250	165	Calibration run
R13	144928	155100	FL250	190	Over coast and snow
Transit to Oulu and land					

Table 8: A382 7th April 1995

Date	Mission Number	Hercules	Skyvan	Do-228	Ground truth	Comments
30/03/95	A376	Y	N	N	N	Clear skies ¹
31/03/95	A377	Y	N	N	N	Clear skies ¹
02/04/95	A378	Y	N	N	N	Snow showers ¹
04/04/95	A379	Y	Y	Y	Y	Snow showers ¹
05/04/95	A380	Y	Y	Y	Y	Sct. cu ¹
06/04/95	A381	Y	Y	Y	Y	Clear skies ²
07/04/95	A382	Y	N	N	N	Sct. snow showers ³

Table 9: MACSI missions

Note 1 Over Finnish sea ice and snow test sites

Note 2 Over open water. Sea ice overflown at high altitude

Note 3 Over Barents sea ice area

10 Flight summaries.

Table 3 summarizes the flights carried out by all the aircraft.

11 Satellite overpass times

Table 4 summarizes the overpass times of DMSP F-10, F-11 and ERS-1 based on predictions by TRKPLT written by Dave Offiler (MRF).

12 Flight track plots.

Flight track plots for all flights are included in appendix A.

13 Weather summaries and synoptic charts.

Weather summaries and synoptic charts for each flight are included in appendix B.

14 Sea ice charts

Sea ice charts for each flight are included in appendix C.

Date	Mission Number	F-10 times	F-11 times	ERS-1 times
30/03/95	A376 ¹	0836 1016 1826	0532 1529	0952 1941
31/03/95	A377 ¹	0945 1935	0530 1516	0920 1910
02/04/95	A378 ¹	0842 1021 1826	0633 1450	0957 1945
04/04/95	A379 ¹	0908 1918	0607 1424 1604	1033 2033
05/04/95	A380 ¹	0856 1035 1846	0615 1432 1612	1013 2003
06/04/95	A381 ²	0856 1035 1846	0614 1432 1613	1012 2003
07/04/95	A382 ³	0925 1100 1235 1410 1555 1730	0710 0845 1025 1205 1345 1525	1035 1215 1355 1535 1710 1850

Table 10: MACSI satellite overpasses

Note 1 Overpass time in area 1: 64N to 67N 22E to 28E

Note 2 Overpass time in area 2: 63N to 66N 21E to 24E

Note 3 Overpass time in area 3: 65N to 80N 24E to 30E

15 Other Information Available

Standard plots have been produced for each flight and these are stored at RSL. For each profile the following parameters have been plotted:

- (i) temperature,
- (ii) dew point,
- (iii) TWC dew point,
- (iv) corrected liquid water content
- (v) Heiman surface temperature
- (vi) Lower BBRs

For each run the following parameters will be available on hardcopy after 1 October 1995:

- (i) MARSS 89 GHz zenith brightness temperature
- (ii) MARSS 89 GHz nadir brightness temperature
- (iii) MARSS 89 GHz nadir $\pm 40^\circ$ brightness temperature
- (iv) MARSS 157 GHz zenith brightness temperature
- (v) MARSS 157 GHz nadir brightness temperature
- (vi) MARSS 157 GHz nadir $\pm 40^\circ$ brightness temperature

For each run the following parameters will be available on hardcopy after 1 December 1995:

- (i) Deimos 24 GHz nadir brightness temperature
- (ii) Deimos 24 GHz nadir $\pm 35^\circ$ brightness temperature
- (iii) Deimos 50 GHz nadir brightness temperature
- (iv) Deimos 50 GHz nadir $\pm 35^\circ$ brightness temperature

To get more information on these or other parameters listed in the EMAC Experimenters Handbook contact Stephen English Telephone (+44) 252 395726 or FAX (+44) 252 515523 or email "senglish@email.meto.govt.uk".

16 Appendix A

Flight track plots.

A376

GPS data
06:41:35 - 15:17:30

Figure 1: A376 30 March 1995 Gulf of Bothnia flight

A377

Figure 2: A377 31 March 1995 Gulf of Bothnia flight

A378

GPS data
08:28:10 - 14:43:00

Figure 3: A378 2 April 1995 Gulf of Bothnia flight

A379

Figure 4: A379 4 April 1995 Gulf of Bothnia intercomparison flight

A380

GPS data
05:37:07 - 13:18:34

Figure 5: A380 5 April 1995 Gulf of Bothnia intercomparison flight

A381

Figure 6: A381 6 April 1995 Clear air flight

43002

GPS data
05.45.13 - 16.08.19

Figure 7: A382 7 April 1995 Barents sea flight

17 Appendix B

Synoptic Weather charts.

Figure 8: A376 30 March 1995 Gulf of Bothnia flight

Polar Stereographic Projection Standard Parallel 80°N Original scale 1:20,000,000

Figure 9: A377 31 March 1995 Gulf of Bothnia flight

ASXX EGRR MSLP ANALYSIS DT 1200 UTC 02 APR 1995

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallel 60°N, Original scale 1:20n

Figure 10: A378 2 April 1995 Gulf of Bothnia flight

Figure 11: A379 4 April 1995 Gulf of Bothnia intercomparison flight

Polar Stereographic Projection, Standard Parallel 60°N, Original Scale 1:200,000

Figure 12: A380 5 April 1995 Gulf of Bothnia intercomparison flight

Figure 13: A381 6 April 1995 Clear air flight

Figure 14: A382 7 April 1995 Barents sea flight

Figure 16: A377 31 March 1995 Gulf of Bothnia flight

Figure 18: A379 4 April 1995 Gulf of Bothnia intercomparison flight

Figure 19: A380 5 April 1995 Gulf of Bothnia intercomparison flight

Figure 21: A382 7 April 1995 Barents sea flight